

Glassy Poly(methacrylate) Terpolymers with Covalently Attached Emitters and Sensitizers for Low-Power Light Upconversion

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^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra of porphyrin intermediates

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectrum (360 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) of mPH_3POH .

Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (75.5 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) of mPH_3POH .

Figure S3. ^1H NMR spectrum (360 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) of mPH_3PMA .

Figure S4. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (75.5 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) of mPH_3PMA .

Absorption spectra of porphyrin monomers

Figure S5. Absorption spectra of solutions of mPH₃PMA (24 μ M) and PdmPH₃PMA (11 μ M) in toluene.

Figure S6. Absorption spectra of solutions of PdmPH₃PMA (red, 11 μ M) and PdOEP (black, 10 μ M) in toluene.

¹H NMR spectra and GPC chromatograms of terpolymers

Figure S7. ¹H NMR spectrum (360 MHz, CD₂Cl₂) of **terpolymer A1**.

Figure S8. ¹H NMR spectrum (360 MHz, CD₂Cl₂) of **terpolymer A2**.

Figure S9. ^1H NMR spectrum (360 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) of **terpolymer A3**.

Figure S10. ^1H NMR spectrum (360 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) of **terpolymer A4**.

Figure S11. ¹H NMR spectrum (360 MHz, CD₂Cl₂) of terpolymer A5.

Figure S12. Gel permeation chromatogram of terpolymer A1.

Figure S13. Gel permeation chromatogram of **terpolymer A2**.

Figure S14. Gel permeation chromatogram of **terpolymer A3**.

Figure S15. Gel permeation chromatogram of **terpolymer A4**.

Figure S16. Gel permeation chromatogram of **terpolymer A5**.

Thermal characterization of chromophores and terpolymers

Figure S17. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) trace of **terpolymer A1** containing 0.73 wt% of PdmPH₃P, and 37 wt% DPA. The TGA experiment was conducted under N₂.

Figure S18. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of **terpolymer A1**, recorded under nitrogen. The polymer was first heated from 25 °C to 200 °C, cooled from 200 °C to 0 °C, and heated again from 0 °C to 250 °C. All heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min.

Figure S19. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of **terpolymer A2**, recorded under nitrogen. The polymer was first heated from 25 °C to 200 °C, cooled from 200 °C to 0 °C, and heated again from 0 °C to 250 °C. All heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min.

Figure S20. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of **terpolymer A3**, recorded under nitrogen. The polymer was first heated from 25 °C to 200 °C, cooled from 200 °C to 0 °C, and heated again from 0 °C to 250 °C. All heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min.

Figure S21. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of **terpolymer A4**, recorded under nitrogen. The polymer was first heated from 25 °C to 200 °C, cooled from 200 °C to 0 °C, and heated again from 0 °C to 250 °C. All heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min.

Figure S22. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of **terpolymer A5**, recorded under nitrogen. The polymer was first heated from 25 °C to 200 °C, cooled from 200 °C to 0 °C, and heated again from 0 °C to 250 °C. All heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min.

Figure S23. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) trace of mPH₃POH. The TGA experiment was conducted under N₂.

Figure S24. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) trace of mPH₃PMA. TGA experiment was conducted under N₂.

Absorption and emission spectra of terpolymers

Figure S25. Absorption spectra of solutions of PdmPH₃PMA (9.7 μ M) and terpolymers **Series A** (0.496 g/L, 1.21 g/L, 1.991 g/L, 2.230 g/L, and 3.172 g/L, respectively) in toluene. The PdmPH₃PMA content in the terpolymers was determined from the absorption at 530 nm, the concentration of the solution, and ϵ of PdmPH₃PMA (28890 mol/L/cm at 530 nm in THF) and approximately equal to 0.73 wt%, 0.11 wt%, 0.05 wt%, 0.45 wt%, and 0.12 wt%.

Figure S26. Normalized absorption spectra of terpolymers **Series A** (0.12 mg/mL in toluene). No baseline correction was applied.

Figure S27. Emission intensity of solution-cast films of terpolymer **Series A** as function of PdmPH₃P content. The films had a thickness of *ca.* 80 μm and the samples were excited at 375 nm.

Figure S28. (a) Absorption spectra of solution-cast films of terpolymer **Series A**. The films had a thickness of *ca.* 80 μm . (b) Absorbance of the β Q-band of **Series A** as a function of PdmPH₃P content.

Figure S29. Phosphorescence spectrum of PdmPH₃PMA crystals recorded upon excitation at 532 nm. The spectrum shows two phosphorescence bands with maxima at 630 and 740 nm.

Figure S30. (a) Absorption spectra of solution-cast films of terpolymer **Series B**. The films had a thickness of *ca.* 80 μ m. (b) Absorbance of the β Q-band of **Series B** as a function of PdmPH₃P content.